

THE DETERMINATION OF AEROSPACE TEAM MEMBERS WITH CYBERSECURITY ACCESS TO CLASSIFIED DATA

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ABSTRACT

The path from a professional in the field to a full-time employee in a respectable governmental organization is not easy. One of the very first challenges that the individual faces while wishing to get hired by The National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA) or any company which stores materials that can be described as classified information is that all professionals have to undergo scrupulous background checks. A method described in this paper explains in detail the backstage of how the determination of establishing security clearances happens and what measures the company takes in order to calculate whether or not the new hire has a need to know certain classified data.

Keywords: Aerospace, cybersecurity, team, recruitment, hire.

I. INTRODUCTION

In governmental agencies and organizations, there are certain types of information which can be described as classified. This type of information must be protected at all costs because this kind of intelligence, if released to the public or given into the wrong hand, can pose a national security threat. The choice of who gets access of classified data relies a carefully planned process which includes background checks, thorough investigations, determining if the employee who is requesting access to see classified data actually has the need to see such data. This paper introduces background checks and the idea of a security clearance and explains why the actions pertaining to classified information are crucial to national security and to the wellbeing of citizens as a whole. The timeline of determining which aerospace team members require and will be granted access to sensitive data varies from company to company. Although, all organizations usually attempt to make their security checks as thorough and as difficult to pass as possible so that classified information never or extremely rarely falls into the wrong hands.

II. METHODOLOGY

A possible method of how a cybersecurity professional can acquire access to classified data, the steps which have to be taken by the company to ensure that the individual truly needs to read, use, and work with the data specified, the thorough background checks conducted by any governmental organization before assigning security clearance to people, are explained in this publication. The analysis and research are conducted utilizing official publications made available to the public and presented on credible governmental websites on the World Wide Web, also known as the Internet, as well as materials published in hard copy. For example, blogs.nasa.gov, www.nasa.gov, www.archives.gov, are some of the official websites listed in this paper. The credibility of the websites used is determined by whether or not they have the .gov at the end of the website link which guarantees that this is indeed a website of the government [1]. Due to a higher number of cybersecurity attacks in the aerospace industry and in the United States as a whole, the topic of this paper was chosen [2]. The hypothetical solution relies heavily on the information given and available to the public through official governmental websites. In this publication, no classified data has been revealed.

III. MODELING AND ANALYSIS

This paper involves a theoretical approach to the creation of models, theories, and observations applicable to the recruiting methods unique to the space industry and whether there are aspects that could be strengthened in these methods. In order to avoid or at least minimize the risk of a malicious hacker becoming a valued professional employee with security clearance and access to classified information, changes in the recruiting process in the aerospace cybersecurity department may be recommended, as stated in this publication. The study explored in this publication is motivated by various hypotheses, one of which is that it is possible to be

employed in a governmental department within a short period of time and access sensitive and even confidential information after passing all the background checks and acquiring the needed security clearance.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

One of the very first concerns that is taken into account when deciding whether or not to give a certain employee access to classified information is if that individual must have access to that data. If the professional has no actual need for reading government data, then, as assured by NASA [3], they are not supposed to have access to it. It typically does not matter what kind of a particular grade, position, or affiliation, the person has - if there is no need for them to access the data, the proper security clearance will not be given to them. The professional's job assignment has to relate directly to the level of classified information for which access is being granted. That way the security clearance is considered to be clearly justified and demonstrates that it is required in order to perform officially assigned duties, for which the employee has already shown "need to execute". Moreover, the person must execute form SF 312 which is a classified information nondisclosure agreement. The document has to be signed by the professional who is in need to know this information and a

witness who guarantees that they witnessed the execution of this agreement by the undersigned [4].

Fig.-1: The Future of Work at NASA [5].

4.1 Training for Employees with Newly Acquired High Security Clearance

All employees with granted access to classified information will undergo special training and will learn how to properly safeguard the classified information provided to them [6]. The professionals will also learn what criminal, civil, and administrative sanctions may be imposed on any individual, whether they belong to the

organization or not, if they fail to protect classified data from unauthorized disclosure. The process of determining whether or not the individual meets the standards for the security clearance and the training process can take some time, with the exact amount of time variant on the organization's timeline. In addition to scrupulous and time-consuming initial background checks, the determination of the "need to know" concern, and the training, all personnel with clearances get reevaluated each year, especially if they had not had the need to access or work with classified information during the previous year [7]. It has been noted in the NASA official documents released to the public that security clearances and access to classified data is not to be retained merely in order for the individual to have access to such classified data should they need it. Those employees who do not have to have access at the current time, are most likely candidates for having their security clearances withdrawn. It is considered to be a normal part of governmental agencies' work and it usually does not arise suspicions if a professional suddenly has their security clearance withdrawn. Moreover, personnel with security clearances high enough to access TS, SCI, or Q (Department of Energy Restricted Data) departments are subject to periodic reinvestigations at any time following the completion of the previous and sometimes initial investigation [8]. Such reinvestigations have to be done no later than five years from the date of the previous investigation or, in simple words, a thorough background check.

4.2 One-time Access to Classified Data

An interesting point to touch is the matter of a one-time classified data access. This type of access is granted on a one-time basis because of the urgent need to read and use the information. There are many restrictions but essentially it does get the individual access to whatever information they may need and / or require in order to complete their governmental task or continue their own project. One of the main difficulties of such one-time access exception is that it may not be issued more than 3 times per a calendar year and it can only be issued for an aggregate time frame of 60 days. In rare cases that the individual requires more than 60 days to complete a certain task or a government mission, the individual will have to be processed for a final security clearance determination which might or might not grant the employee access to classified data for an extended period of time [9]. Also, another important requirement of the one-time or a short-term access to classified governmental information is that the employee who is requesting to view and work with the data is a U.S. citizen who has been continuously employed by the Federal Government for the preceding 24 months. It is important to note that employees which acquire the one-time access to classified data may then attain a short-term security clearance to continue working with the data requires, but only if the department feels there is a need to keep that certain individual working with the classified information.

Fig.-2: The Use of Sensitive Data at Home, NASA [10].

4.3 Codes for Classified Data

There are several codes for classified information. These codes divide the types of data in terms of the secrecy and how much of a threat the individual with the data possessed might be. The classification of information system in the United States of America has three classification levels -- Top Secret, Secret, and Confidential -- which are defined in a document titled EO 12356 [11]. There are also codes for each level of position sensitivity, designated specifically for national security positions. Such national security positions are divided into 3

groups and designated as non-critical sensitive, critical sensitive, or special sensitive. Professionals who wish to acquire security clearance to be in one of these three groups are vetted differently [12]. Special-sensitive (typically abbreviated as SS) refers to positions which require access to the highest level of clearance and which demand access to Top Secret Sensitive Compartmented Information (TS/SCI). In this case, each individual wishing to acquire such a clearance will undergo Single Scope Background Investigation, also called SSBI, which is one of the most thorough investigations currently existent in the United States. The investigation happens after the individual submits Standard Form 86 (SF-86). All individuals in this group need to be approved through the investigation before getting any kind of access to TS/SCI.

Employee Type	Total Eligibility			
	As of 10/1/13:		As of 10/1/14:	
	Conf/Secret	Top Secret	Conf/Secret	Top Secret
Government	2,886,106	851,920	2,412,126	771,151
Contractor	558,626	497,683	483,185	456,700
Other	175,859	180,185	212,375	179,039
Sub-Total:	3,620,591	1,529,788	3,107,686	1,406,890
Total:	5,150,379		4,514,576	

Fig.-3: Number of people with access to US classified data (USA) [13].

The critical-sensitive group (abbreviated as CS) currently refers to positions which require access to Top Secret (TS) or North Atlantic Treaty Organization (NATO) information. The professionals in this section undergo a SSBI, using SF-86, and although this section is considered to be somewhat of an easier one to get access to, the investigation is thorough and may take some time, depending on the organization. The third group is the noncritical-sensitive group and it includes positions which need access to Secret, Confidential, or NATO Secret/Confidential information. This group is open to access for new hires, but they still need to undergo at a minimum, an ANACI (Access National Agency Check with Inquiries), using SF-86 in e-QIP which is a web-based automated system that the professional can use to fill out SF-86, before even taking a glance to look at classified information [14]. In addition, there is another group which is called the non-sensitive group and it relates to any position which does not require access to data which could become a national security threat. Positions in the last group are not considered to be national security positions.

V. CONCLUSION

The determination of which employee should have a security clearance high enough to have access to classified data can be a challenge for many governmental organizations. The main priority is to determine whether or not the employee actually has a need to see the requested information. Access to security clearance is never given just “in case” the employee needs it. Each employee must demonstrate a need to work with the data specified. In some cases, that need may be urgent and so a one-time access pass may be issued. The benefit of such a pass is that it is much quicker to acquire compared to a regular security clearance which can take some time, depending on the timeline for the background checks and the investigations. There are also three main groups which explain the positions which require certain security clearances - non-critical sensitive, critical sensitive, or special sensitive. The non-critical group refers to position which needs access to sensitive information, however that information is considered to be the least dangerous out of the three groups. The next group is the critical sensitive group which is harder to get access to than the non-critical sensitive group, although it is still a challenge, especially if the employee is a relatively new hire. The third and last described in detail group is the special sensitive group, members of which have access to the most secure data. The professionals who wish to get a security clearance high enough to read classified data in the special sensitive group must undergo extensive background checks and their investigations are of utmost scrupulousness. In conclusion, it is and should be hard to determine who should have access to classified data in the aerospace industry.

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Together we can do anything. #Elbrus2021

VI. REFERENCES

- [1] Rachenko, Y. (2021). How A New Hire Can Acquire Classified Data In Aerospace Industry. International Research Journal of Modernization in Engineering Technology and Science, 3(1), 1138-1141, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4485131>
- [2] Rushikesh Gajanan Lavhale. (2020). Influence Of Artificial Intelligence In Manufacturing Industries. International Engineering Journal For Research & Development, Volume 5, Issue 1, p. 3.
- [3] NASA Office of Protective Services. (August 2020). NPR 1600.3 -- Chapter3. Personnel Security Investigations for National Security Positions. NASA, https://nodis3.gsfc.nasa.gov/npg_img/N_PR_1600_0003_/N_PR_1600_0003_chapter3.pdf
- [4] Perakovic, D. (2021). Ensemble machine learning approach for classification of IoT devices in smart home. Springer, <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s13042-020-01241-0>
- [5] Skytland, N. (2019). The Future of Work. NASA, <https://blogs.nasa.gov/futureofwork/category/future-of-work/>
- [6] Rachenko, Y. (2020). Enhancing the Efficiency of the Current Method of Establishing Team Members in Aerospace Communications. 4th International Scientific and Practical Conference, pp. 69-72, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4483002>
- [7] Ahmad, T. (2020). A Compact Frequency Reconfigurable PIFA Antenna for Heterogeneous Applications. IEEE Asia-Pacific Microwave Conference, <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/abstract/document/9331510>
- [8] Internet System Design for the Disabled Net. Proceedings of the International Conference on Software Engineering Research and Practice, SERP '03, June 23 - 26, 2003, Las Vegas, Nevada, USA, Volume 2, Runa Jesmin
- [9] Rachenko, Y. (2021). Using a Computerized System to Determine the Most Suitable Job Skills for Aerospace Industry. 6th International Scientific and Practical Conference, pp. 210-213, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4485088>
- [10] NASA. (2018). Don't let data slip through your fingers. NASA, https://www.nasa.gov/sites/default/files/atoms/files/373448_oct-dec_2018_it_talk.pdf
- [11] Federal Register. (2016). Executive Order 12356. National Archives, <https://www.archives.gov/federal-register/codification/executive-order/12356.html>
- [12] Accessible and Usable Internet System Design. Conference Paper. Proceedings of the IADIS International Conference WWW/Interne, ICWI, Algarve, Portugal. Runa Jesmin
- [13] Kravets, D. (2015). Number of people with access to US classified data down 12% in one year. ARS Technica, <https://arstechnica.com/tech-policy/2015/05/people-with-access-to-us-classified-data-plunges-12-percent-in-one-year/>
- [14] Ahmad, T. (2019). Fuzzy-Logic Based Localization for Mobile Sensor Networks. 2nd International Conference on Communication, Computing and Digital systems, <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/abstract/document/8681024>